

Processes and pathways to disseminate science for wide and efficient reuse

Romain David

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PARSEC is a project sponsored by the **Belmont Forum** as part of its Collaborative Research Action (CRA) on Science-Driven e-Infrastructures Innovation (SEI), with funding from **FAPESP**, the **ANR**, **JST** and the **NSF**, with collaborators from Australia, and support from the **synthesis centre CESAB** of the **French Foundation for Research on Biodiversity (FRB)**.

We acknowledge the Traditional Owners and Custodians of the land and sea in all nations. We honour their profound connections to land, water, biodiversity and culture and pay our respects to their Elders past, present and emerging.

Processes and pathways to disseminate science for wide and efficient reuse

ERINHA is a RI of biocontainment laboratories which specialize in infectious disease research

BSL-4

BSL-3

ex. Ebola, Nipah, Marburg, Crimean Congo Hemorrhagic Fever

ex. HIV, H1N1 Influenza, Yersinia pestis, Rabies

ex. Influenza, Hepatitis, Salmonella, Measles, Mumps

ex. Non pathogenic E. coli, nonpathogenic bacteria

Biocontainment laboratories:

- Unique buildings with complex engineering systems maintaining 'containment'
- Increased personnel and information security
- Nationally and internationally regulated

Romain David - Data Steward / scientist at ERINHA / EOSC-Life european programm

Summarised roles:

- define and implement ERINHA data strategy
- manage all data related activities
- be the technical representative for ERINHA in collaborative European projects (EOSC-Life, ERINHA-Advance, By-Covid, ISIDORe).
 - For EOSC Life, mainly WP1, WP4 and secondary wp 6, **can provide resources and work for others** (case studies, adoptions cases, advising and expertise e.g. PARSEC)

EOSC-Life Life Science Research Infrastructures and Objectives

- Establish EOSC-Life by publishing FAIR life science data resources in EOSC
- Provide the policies, guidelines and processes for secure and ethical data reuse
- Populate an ecosystem of innovative life-science tools in EOSC
- Enable data-driven research in Europe by connecting life scientists to EOSC via open calls for participation

Processes and pathways to disseminate science for wide and efficient reuse

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Disseminate Science:
Why? How ?

02

Tools and processes

03

Good practices and
lessons to be learned

- The good
- The bad
- The ugly

Processes and pathways to disseminate science for wide and efficient reuse

Why publish your scientific outputs?

- To be read
- To participate in the debate
- To propose your theories
- To be reused
- To build collaborations
- To share
- To be known
- I have to as it is mandated
- **To build a common future**
- ...

Processes and pathways to disseminate science for wide and efficient reuse

Think about your dissemination plan

In the *real world*

- Paper journal (!)
- Books, posters
- Seminars and talks
- Talking with colleagues

In the *digital world* (mainly!)

- Remote seminar and talks
- Emails and other exchanges with colleagues
- Websites (project, personal page, e-box...)
- Social media in research field / internet dissemination tools & relays
- All real world document adapted to the digital world

Processes and pathways to disseminate science for wide and efficient reuse

The WWW - internet

This machine is a server DO NOT Power DOWN!

Number of Internet Hosts

Source	http://www.isc.org/index.pl?/ops/ds/host-count-history.php
Author	Ansgar Hellwig

Processes and pathways to disseminate science for wide and efficient reuse

International
fora

Building the social and technical bridges to enable open sharing and re-use of data

RDA EU RDA US CONTACT US LOGIN REGISTRATION

RDA
RESEARCH DATA ALLIANCE

O&A Members 71
Active Organisational & Affiliate members

MEMBERSHIP Members: 12863
Becoming a member of RDA is simple and open to both individuals and organizations
[Register now](#)

RDA Groups WG & IGs: 100
Discover what RDA Working and Interest Groups and all other Groups are up to and find out how to join them. [Explore Groups](#)

ABOUT RDA ▾ GET INVOLVED ▾ GROUPS ▾ RECOMMENDATIONS & OUTPUTS ▾ RDA FOR DISCIPLINES ▾ PLENARIES & EVENTS ▾ NEWS & MEDIA ▾

'A Decade of Data':
Celebrating 10 Years of the
Research Data Alliance

A Decade of Data 2013-2023

Learn more about upcoming
international and regional events

The Research Data Alliance is a global organization with over 12,400 members from 145 countries, and is built on principles that include openness, inclusivity and transparency.

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Metadata: the *sine qua non* condition for effective dissemination

Idea: Frederic De Lamotte

Impact of numeric content to describe your work

If you're writing something on Google Docs, set it as a book, a blog, an essay, a report, or anything else. The formatting can be as important as the writing itself.

One important part of that formatting is the spacing between your words. Spacing off writing can make it easier to read and digest, and help people think a little more about the source and impact of what you're saying. One way to help to facilitate that understanding in your formatting is by adding page breaks.

Adding a page to your work is simple, and can help to convey the end of one topic or the start of the beginning of another. You've probably seen page breaks in chapter books all your life.

If you're wondering how to add a page to your own work, here's how to do it.

>95%

<5%

<0.1%

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Zenodo:
a key component

<https://zenodo.org/>

DOI system

zenodo Search Upload Communities Log in Sign up

Communities created and curated by Zenodo users

parsec

Showing 0 to 1 out of 1 communities. Sort by

PARSEC: Building New Tools for Data Sharing and Re-use through a Transnational Investigation of the Socioeconomic Impacts of Protected Areas View

The PARSEC project is designed to provide a unique opportunity for data and synthesis scientists to collaborate and exchange in real-time toward the goal of improving research outcomes, data sharing, and data reuse. It will also help pioneer new...

Want your own community? Sign Up

It's easy. Just click the button to get started.

- **Curate** – accept/reject what goes in your community collection.
- **Export** – your community collection is automatically exported via OAI-PMH
- **Upload** – get custom upload link to send to people

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Twitter

Dr Romain DAVID
@Romain_DAVID_13

Marine & terrestrial [#Ecology](#), scientific diver & Datascientist / manager
[@ERINHA_RI](#) T&RT myview [#FAIRdata](#) [#BigData](#) [#Graph](#) [orcid.org/0000-0003-4073...](#)

Montignac, France [cv.archives-ouvertes.fr/romain-david/](#)
Naissance le 8 février 1976 [A rejoint Twitter en mai 2013](#)

4 849 abonnements 1 898 abonnés

Tweets Tweets et réponses Médias J'aime

Tweet épinglé
Dr Romain DAVID @Romain_DAVID_13 · 1 oct.
Please RT [@erinha](#) [@Parsec](#) [@EoecLife](#) poster Milestone: 500 views!
Multilingual Data Challenges in Professionalizing Data Stewardship
worldwide [dol.org/10.5281/zenodo...](#) who want to participate to our next
inter*** paper? [#FAIR](#) [#DataScience](#)

MULTILINGUAL CHALLENGES
PROFESSIONALIZING DATA STEWARDSHIP AT THE GLOBAL SCALE
The use of Principle G vocabulary on multiple Data Stew dictionary
My name is C3F I am fluent in one million forms of communications... you!

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LinkedIn (and others)

More

- CV
- Longer articles
- ! add links
- ! add images
- ! recommend
- ! Daily network build

The screenshot shows a LinkedIn profile for Romain DAVID Ph. D., a Research fellow at ERINHA AISBL. The profile displays two publications:

- Pan-regional marine benthic cryptobiome biodiversity patterns revealed by metabarcoding Autonomous Reef Monitoring Structures**
Molecular Ecology, Wiley · 15 oct. 2020
Action: [Afficher la publication](#)
- Autres auteurs** (with 7 other authors)
- FAIRness Literacy: The Achilles' Heel of Applying FAIR Principles**
CODATA Data Science Journal, Committee on Data for Science and Technology (CODATA) · 11 août 2020
Action: [Afficher la publication](#)
- Autres auteurs** (with 7 other authors)

At the bottom of the profile, there is a link: [Afficher les 31 publications](#) →

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Researchgate

- Based on communities
- Number of
 - Views
 - Citations
 - Downloads
- Recommendation(s)
- Saving system
- Request of private text
- Communities building
- Scoring

DOI (not recommended)

Processes and pathways to disseminate science for wide and efficient reuse

National archives / connected archives

AFFILIATIONS

Institut méditerranéen de biodiversité et d'écologie marine et continentale (1)
European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents (1)
Mathématiques, Informatique et Statistique pour l'Environnement et l'Agronomie (2)
Université de Montpellier (2)
Institut national d'études supérieures agronomiques de Montpellier (1)
Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement (1)
Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique (1)

RESEARCHER IDENTIFIERS

- IGHAL : romain-david
- ResearcherID : ABH-8335-2020
- ORCID : 0000-0003-4073-7456
- Google Scholar : <https://scholar.google.fr/citations?user=rng7BuJcAAAAAJ&hl=fr>
- IDP INRA : rodavid
- IdRef : 233679259

SOCIAL NETWORKS

- Twitter
- Google
- LinkedIn
- Blog
- ResearchGate
- Academia

EXPORT PUBLICATIONS

Export the displayed publications:

- XML(TeX)
- BibTeX
- EndNote
- CSV
- HTML

Romain DAVID,

Research fellow - Data Manager at ERINHA AISBL (European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents)

- Developing a data management plan for ERINHA
- Implementing ERINHA data catalogue.
- Developing cloud-compatible, FAIR-compliant data resources.
- Ensuring data security, including restricting access to certain data as necessary, data recovery, secure storage and methodologies for the transfer of sensitive data.
- Identifying and implementing relevant e-tools and e-infrastructures for ERINHA data management
- WP Leader of the european program ISIDORE
- Task Leader of the european program By-COVID
- Co-chair in R.D.A. IG SHARC (SHaring for Rewarding and Credits Interest Group in Research Data Alliance)
- Co-chair in R.D.A. IG PDS (Professionalising Data Stewardship Interest Group in Research Data Alliance)
- Co-chair in R.D.A. IG SD (Sensitive Data Interest Group in Research Data Alliance)
- Co-chair of the list "RDA France Santé" -> Register here: RDA France Santé
- Co-chair of the list "RDA France FAIR Data" -> Register here: RDA France FAIR Data
- Member of the EOSC Task Force FAIR Metrics and Data Quality
- Membre of FDO Forum sous groupe "FDO type" et "FDO Sem"

before Research fellow at INRAE (Institut National de Recherche pour l'Agriculture, l'Alimentation et l'Environnement) MISTEA laboratory (UMR Mathématiques, Informatique et Statistique pour l'Environnement et l'Agronomie)

- Interoperability improvement for platforms (Phenotyping Hybrid Information System), ensure links between actors of different disciplines.
- Develop activities on the development, adoption, choice and implementation of ontologies and standards.
- Take part in the development of domain standards
- Co-chair du R.D.A. IG Group SHARC (SHaring for Rewarding and Credits Interest Group in Research Data Alliance)

before Ph.D. Oceanography - Data mining at the Ecology and Environment Institute of the CNRS. IMBE (UMR 7263) laboratory

- Initiator and moderator of the IndexMed consortium which has since become IndexMEED
- Co-chair of the R.D.A. IG Group SHARC (SHaring for Rewarding and Credits Interest Group in Research Data Alliance)
- WP Leader of the European program CIGESMED.
- Administrator of various databases for coastal observation systems.

Area of activity

My work concerns large-scale observation and experimentation systems of terrestrial and marine (agro)ecosystems and information systems and the dissemination of biodiversity knowledge coupled with them. I am particularly interested in new methods of data mining and data representation in the form of graphs. This formalization of knowledge makes it possible to envisage the use of new methods to analyze heterogeneous data, to propose scientific questions emerging from the data (and not the reverse, which is the classical scientific approach), and to make Scenario proposals dependent on contextual variables that can be used in the area of decision support. I wish to continue to invest in the development of multidisciplinary research programs and partnerships involving scientists and

en Sign in 73

EUROPEAN PROJECTS

- EOSC-Life - Providing an open collaborative space for digital biology in Europe (1)
- Coralligenous based indicators to evaluate and monitor the "good ecological status" of the Me-diterranean coastal waters (2)
- DEVELOPMENT Of innovative Tools for understanding marine biodiversity and assessing good Environmental Status (2)
- ERINHA-Advance - Advancing European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents (1)
- RDA Europe 4 0 (2)
- European Plant Phenotyping Network 2020 (1)
- European Plant Phenotyping Network (1)
- European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement (1)

KEYWORDS

Sensitive data Data qualification EOSC-Life
Graphs Data science Basins Mediterranean
Sea Coralligenous habitats Life sciences
Coralligenous Interoperability
Biodiversity Metabarcoding Citizen science
Graph Toolbox Data sharing Accessible
Monitoring FAIR (Full list)

AMR PROJECTS

- Coralligenous based indicators to evaluate and monitor the "good ecological status" of the Me-diterranean coastal waters (2)
- Des Données aux Connaissances en Agronomie et Biodiversité (1)
- Dispositif de recherche interdisciplinaire sur les Interactions Hommes-Milieu (1)

- DZKAB - Data to Knowledge in Agronomy and Biodiversity project create a framework to turn agronomy and biodiversity data into knowledge –semantically described, interoperable, actionable, open– and investigate scientific methods and tools to exploit this knowledge for applications in science & agriculture
- EPPN2020 - (UMR MISTEA part) European Plant Phenotyping Network (Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 731013)
- IndexMed - Indexing for Mining Ecological and Environmental Data : www.indexmed.eu (Funding 2016 - MI du CNRS)
- GRAMINEES - GRAPhe data Mining In Natural, Ecological and Environmental Sciences (Funding GDR MADICS)
- EVACOR et EVACOR2 - EVALuation des services écosystémiques des habitats CORalligènes (1 et 2)
- VIGI-GEEK - Visualisation of Graph In transdisciplinary Global Ecology, Economy and Sociology data-Kernel (D66 Imag'in, Funding MI du CNRS)
- CHARLIE - CHAnge de Regard En Liant dans Indexmed l'Environnement et les Etoiles (PEPS Blanc, Funding INEE - CNRS)
- CIGESMED - Coralligenous based Indicators to evaluate and monitor the "Good Environmental Status" of the MEDITERRANEAN coastal waters (ANR conventions n° 12-SEAS-0001-01, 02 and 03 for France, GSRT - 12SEAS-12-C2 for Greece; TUBITAK Project No: 112Y393 for Turkey)
- DEVOTES - DEvelopment Of innovative Tools for understanding marine biodiversity and assessing good Environmental Status www.devotes-project.eu (European Union's Seventh Framework Programme for research, technological development and demonstration under grant agreement n°306392)
- Proteker - Effects of global change on the marine benthos and habitats in Kerguelen Islands: Establishment of a base line for ecological and genetic monitoring, protection and conservation. www.proteker.net (Programme IPEV 1044)

You will find the slides of the oral presentations - not accepted in hal on researchgate: Romain David on ResearchGate

THESES

Romain David. De la conception d'un système d'observation à large échelle au déploiement et à l'exploitation de son système d'information : application à l'observation des habitats coralligènes et à la colonisation de récifs artificiels (ARMS). Biodiversité et Ecologie. Aix Marseille Université, 2018. Français. (tel-18139376)

JOURNAL ARTICLES

- J. Machicao, A. Ben Abbes, L. Meneguzzi, P.L.P. Corrêa, A. Specht, et al. Mitigation Strategies to Improve Reproducibility of Poverty Estimations From Remote Sensing Images Using Deep Learning. *Earth and Space Science*, American Geophysical Union/Wiley, 2022, 9 (8), pp e2022EA002379. (10.1029/2022ea002379). (hal-03761874)
- Christian Ohmann, Romain David, Mónica Cano Abadía, Florence Bietrix, Jan-Willem Bolten, et al. Pilot Study on the Interpolation of a Categorisation System for FAIRer Digital Objects Related to Sensitive Data in the Life Sciences. *Journal of Data Intelligence*, Paramus NJ: Rinton Press, 2022, 4 (2), pp 196 - 211. (10.1162/dint_a_00126). (hal-03663659)
- Jeaneth Machicao, Alison Seocht, Danton Vellenich, Leandro Meneuzzi, Romain David, et al. A Deep-Learning Method

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ORCID

The screenshot shows the 'Works' section of an ORCID profile, displaying 50 items. A context menu is open over the first work, offering options: Search & link, Add DOI, Add PubMed ID, Add BibTeX, and Add manually. The first work is titled 'Kakila database: Towards a FAIR community approved database of cetacean presence in the waters of the Guadeloupe Archipelago, based on citizen science'. It is a journal article from Biodiversity Data Journal (2021) with DOI: 10.3897/bdjl.9.e69022. Contributors include Lorraine Coché, Elie Arnaud, Laurent Bouveret, Romain David, Eric Foulquier, Nadège Gandilhon, Etienne Jeannesson, Yvan Le Bras, Emilie Lerigoleur, and Pascal Lopez et al. The second work is 'Whales and dolphins: beautiful sentinel species to be studied in the framework of a coastal zone observatory, but very complex to approach', a conference paper from 2021-09-06.

The screenshot shows a full ORCID iD profile for Romain David. The profile includes:

- ORCID iD:** https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4073-7456
- Emails:** romain.david@erinha.eu, david.romain@gmail.com
- Websites & social links:** HAL, LinkedIn, Twitter, Google Scholar, ResearchGate, GitHub, Academia, OSF, High Pathogenic Agent FIP.
- Other IDs:** Scopus Author ID: 57189222154
- Keywords:** Oceanography, Biodiversity, Data Management, Data curation, Data sciences, Open sciences, FAIR principles, Ecology, Data mining.
- Biography:** My work concerns large-scale observation and experimentation systems of terrestrial and marine (agro)ecosystems and information systems and the dissemination of biodiversity knowledge coupled with them. I am particularly interested in new methods of data mining and data representation in the form of graphs. This formalization of knowledge makes it possible to envisage the use of new methods to analyze heterogeneous data, to propose scientific questions emerging from the data (and not the reverse, which is the classical scientific approach), and to make Scenario proposals dependent on contextual variables that can be used in the area of decision support. I wish to continue to invest in the development of multidisciplinary research programs and partnerships involving scientists and public actors. FAIR data management and open science addict and "Data Management Plan with FAIR Compliance" evangelizer. Co-chair in R.D.A. IG SHARC (SHARING for Rewarding and Credits Interest Group in Research Data Alliance) Co-chair in R.D.A. IG PDS (Professionalising Data Stewardship Interest Group in Research Data Alliance) Co-chair in R.D.A. IG SD (Sensitizing Data Interest Group in Research Data Alliance) Co-chair of the list "RDA France Santé" -> Register here: RDA France Santé Co-chair of the list "RDA France FAIR Data" -> Register here: RDA France FAIR Data Member of the EOSC Task Force FAIR Metrics and Data Quality Member of FDO Forum sous groupe "FDO type" et "FDO Sem"
- Employment (5):** European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents (ERINHA): Paris, FR (2020-05-01 to present) | Data manager / data scientist (Data Management); National Institute for Agronomical and Environmental Research (INRAE): Montpellier, FR (2019-03-21 to 2020-03-21) | Research Fellow (Ingénieur de Recherche) (UMR Mathématiques, Informatique et Statistique pour l'Environnement et l'Agronomie (MISTEA)).

Airiti, BASE - Bielefeld Academic Search Engine, Crossref
Metadata Search, DOE / OSTI, DataCite, Deutsche
Nationalbibliothek (DNB), Europe PubMed Central, HAL, ISNI,
JalC, MLA International Bibliography, OpenAIRE Explore,
Redalyc, Research Data Australia, Scopus - Elsevier, The Lens.

VI WORKSHOP ON DATA SCIENCE AND MACHINE LEARNING-PARSEC, 03-06 October 2022, São Paulo, Brazil
Romain David - ERINHA - romain.david@erinha.eu @romain_david13 <http://www.erinha.eu>

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A link to zenodo in your mailing!

Accueil | Dépôt | Consultation ▾ | Recherche | Documentation

hal-02885254, version 1

Pré-publication, Document de travail ⓘ

AND IN ZENODO PARSEC Data and Digital Output Management Plan and Workbook

Shelley Stall ¹, Corrêa Pedro Luiz Pizzigatti ², Alison Specht ³, Romain David ^{4,5}, Rorie Edmunds ⁶, Laurence Mabile ^{7,8}, Jeaneth Machicao ², Margaret O'Brien ⁹, Lesley Wyborn ¹⁰ [Details](#)

- 1 American Geophysical Union
- 2 University of Sao Polo
- 3 Centre for Marine Science, School of Biological Sciences, University of Queensland
- 4 MISTEA - Mathématiques, Informatique et Statistique pour l'Environnement et l'Agronomie
- 5 ERINHA-AISBL - European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents
- 6 WDS - World Data System International Program Office
- 7 INSERM - Institut National de la Santé et de la Recherche Médicale
- 8 UT3 - Université Toulouse III - Paul Sabatier
- 9 UCSB - University of California [Santa Barbara]
- 10 ANU - Australian National University

Abstract : PARSEC Data and Digital Output Management Plan and Workbook for the Belmont Forum Collaborative Research Action (CRA) Science-driven e-Infrastructure Innovation (SEI) for the Enhancement of Transnational, Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Data Use in Environmental Change Project Building New Tools for Data Sharing and Reuse through a Transnational Investigation of the Socioeconomic Impacts of Protected Areas (PARSEC) This Data and Digital Output Management Plan and Workbook (DDOMP) are used by the PARSEC team to establish the policies the team will follow, document the operational procedures necessary to comply with those policies, and the planned activities necessary to manage PARSEC data, software, and other digital outputs. This is a working document. This document describes activities necessary during the PARSEC research lifecycle as well as those necessary to preserve all digital outputs for use into the future. It is the intent of the PARSEC team to make our digital outputs as open as possible, discoverable, accessible, well-documented to promote the broadest reuse. These elements are both recommended and required by the Belmont Forum Open Data Policy and Principles[1] and the FAIR Guiding Principles[2]. The Belmont Forum Open Data Policy and Principles state that: Datasets should be: Discoverable through catalogues and search engines Accessible as open data by default, and made available with minimum time delay Understandable in a way that allows researchers—including those outside the discipline of origin—to use them Manageable and protected from loss for future use in sustainable, trustworthy repositories

Keywords : [Synthesis science](#) [Data science](#) [Socio-economic](#) [outcomes](#) [Protected areas](#) [Data management](#) [Transnational](#) [Transdisciplinary](#)

Type de document : [Pré-publication, Document de travail](#)

FICHIER

PARSEC Data and Digital Output...
Fichiers produits par l'(les) auteur(s)

LICENCE

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IDENTIFIANTS

- HAL Id : hal-02885254, version 1
- DOI : [10.5281/zenodo.3891427](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3891427)

COLLECTIONS

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VI WORKSHOP ON DATA SCIENCE AND MACHINE LEARNING-PARSEC, 03-06 October 2022, São Paulo, Brazil

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[@romain_david13](https://twitter.com/romain_david13)

<http://www.erinha.eu>

Processes and pathways to disseminate science for wide and efficient reuse

SCIENTIFIC
DATA

Comment | [Open Access](#) | Published: 15 March 2016

Process:
FAIR principles
(Wilkinson *et al.*, 2016)

The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship

Mark D. Wilkinson, Michel Dumontier, [...] Barend Mons

Scientific Data **3**, Article number: 160018 (2016) | [Cite this article](#)

98k Accesses | **1296** Citations | **1492** Altmetric | [Metrics](#)

 An Addendum to this article was published on 19 March 2019

**Numerical dissemination
must be FAIR !**

Abstract

There is an urgent need to improve the infrastructure supporting the reuse of scholarly data. A diverse set of stakeholders—representing academia, industry, funding agencies, and scholarly publishers—have come together to design and jointly endorse a concise and measurable set of principles that we refer to as the FAIR Data Principles. The intent is that these may act as a guideline for those wishing to enhance the reusability of their data holdings. Distinct from peer initiatives that

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Process:

Community building And FAIR principles (David et al., 2022)

First
PARSEC
Paper

Rich
Metadata
ID (links)
Provenance
Licence
Community
standards

Process	Steps
Preparing FAIRification	Explain FAIRification
	Define constraints
	Define advantages
Training	Increase FAIR literacy Convince partners
Pre-FAIRifying	Building shared strategy
	Define community
	Define objects and variables
	Select items to be identified
	Analyse common denominators
FAIRifying	Do: Downward levelling
	Check: first interoperations
	Adjust: Identifying gaps and new expectation

Wheel of the FAIRification processes

Processes and pathways to disseminate science for wide and efficient reuse

Process:
Impact assessment
and improvement

Google Scholar

<https://scholar.google.fr/>

Romain DAVID

Data Manager at ERINHA (European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents)
Adresse e-mail validée de erinha.eu - [Page d'accueil](#)
[biodiversity](#) [marine ecology](#) [FAIR](#) [Data sciences](#) [open sciences](#)

	Toutes	Depuis 2017
Citations	476	449
indice h	11	11
indice i10	11	11

ANNÉE	CITÉE PAR
2016	149
2018	43
2017	34
2014	29
2017	23
2020	20

Accès public **TOUT AFFICHER**

0 article non disponibles / 27 articles disponibles

Sur la base des exigences liées au financement

Coauteurs **MODIFIER**

Jean-Pierre FERAL
Directeur de Recherche CNRS é...

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Process: Impact
assessment
and improvement

Altmetric

www.altmetric.com/

Processes and pathways to disseminate science for wide and efficient reuse

outputs scored by Altmetric

scholarly data. A... [show]

MORE...

Mentioned by

- 118 news outlets
- 67 blogs
- 19 policy sources
- 992 tweeters
- 1 patent
- 19 Facebook pages
- 26 Wikipedia pages
- 5 Google+ users
- 1 Redditor
- 1 research highlight platform
- 1 Q&A thread
- 2 video uploaders

Citations

- 5776 Dimensions

Readers on

- 5256 Mendeley

TWITTER DEMOGRAPHICS

MENDELEY READERS

ATTENTION SCORE IN CONTEXT

The data shown below were collected from the profiles of **992** tweeters who shared this research output. [Click here to find out more about how the information was compiled.](#)

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Good practices and challenges for sharing multidisciplinary scientific data: how the QUAMPO project fits into the FAIR and open science movement?

EPINOUX C. (a), CASTREC J. (b), DAVID R. (c), FONTAINE Q. (b), FULLGRABE L. (b), GOBERT S. (d), LE FLOCH S. (e), LEJEUNE P. (b), MADON B. (a), MARENGO M. (b), PIGNON-MUSSAUD C. (a), PILLET M. (a, b), THOMAS H. (a)

- QUAMPO: Multi-biomarkers approach to define the ecological status of Corsican ports
- Relied on a set of practices and faced number of challenges in order to share FAIR and open science data

Objective: offers the managers and the scientific community the first, to our knowledge, completely open database on marine biomarkers

Data dictionary

Challenges encountered:

- Difference of vocabularies in a multidisciplinary project
- Changing protocols during an experimental project

Solutions:

- Use of the Darwin Core, of ontologies and of Skos
- Use or creation of DOIs

Take home message: international and national outreach of the database by its opening to other monitoring projects

Analysis of a specimen of *Mytilus galloprovincialis*

Data paper

Challenges encountered:

- Collaboration of a large and geographically distant team

Solutions:

- Paper sprint: collaborative method of writing an article

Open database

Challenges encountered:

- Opening of not-FAIR data
- Making FAIR and public data originally made for internal use
- Create a base able to host other similar projects
- Accessibility of private data

Solutions:

- Curation (cleaning + enhancement) of data
- Universal variable naming
- Adding some data from the QUALIPERTUIS project of the LIENSs
- Data "as open as possible, as closed as necessary"

References

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- (b) Station de Recherches Sous-marines et Océanographiques (STARESO), Pointe Revellotta, BP 33, 20260 Calvi, France
- (c) European Research Infrastructure on Highly Pathogenic Agents (ERINHA), 98 rue du Trône B-1050 Bruxelles, Belgium
- (d) Oceanology Department, MARE centre, University of Liège, 15 Allée du 6 Août, Sart Tilman, B6c, 4000 Liège, Belgium
- (e) Centre of Documentation, Research and Experimentation on Accidental Water Pollution (CEDRE), 715 rue Alain Colas, CS 41836, 29218 Brest cedex 2, France

New efficient tools:

- Data papers
- Data sprints
- Radical collaborations

Epinox et al., 2022

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Processes and pathways to disseminate science for wide and efficient reuse

Multilingual Data Challenges

in Professionalizing Data Stewardship worldwide

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Twitter: @PARSEC_News @ERINHA_R

My name is C-3PO!
I am fluent in over six million forms of communication... And you?

The "TERM WARS" at global Scale: a time and space story

Discrepancies between regions and groups (culture, content, workflows, language, semantics, translation, funds...) are numerous whether for individual data users or more universally. We must anticipate issues such as **which is the preferred language**, **polysemy** (1 term, multiple meanings), **confusion** (multiple terms for 1 meaning or 'false friends' between 2 languages), **both existing and evolving nuances** (not an exact match between languages and during time). Furthermore, terms are often **adopted from another language with different contexts and disciplinary realms** (that might decrease interoperability and impedes translation of all versions at the same time).

Translation occurs at the concept level, not as a simple one to one translation of (consecutive) words.

Context: regions / disciplines and / or languages

Over time, research evolves, disciplines are created, split and new terms are necessary to describe new concepts...

Technical challenges

Challenges

- How to choose the best vocabulary / ontology resource?
- How to manage different preferences between communities?
- How to translate sustainably, mindful of inherent instability?

Convergence result

Standardized vocabulary worldwide

[standards do it better!](#)

Good practices

For translators:

- Scientific skills with at least good command of target languages
- Validators to check work translated
- A clear versioning system
- A translating strategy with prioritization levels

For Databases:

- Data dictionary with
 - disambiguated definitions both linked to and linked by concepts in shared ontologies
 - the date of the definition
 - the context of use (disciplinary - protocol - necessary skills...)
- A description of the community approval process that can be adopted for new terms by other communities

Science must be universally shared, in an interdisciplinary way, respecting that all disciplines are creating new concepts. The fact that science is always creating them is the core challenge for translators

Translation challenges are also organisational and sustainability challenges:

Care must be taken to ensure that datasets resulting from projects that practice co-creation and co-evolution of knowledge are translated into indigenous languages such that they can be used by the affected communities. Taking these challenges into account, we have to consider **human effort and the level of translation**, e.g. a low or minimum yet sustainable level, that is **legally allowable**. How can such minimal objectives be linked with FAIR principle compliance (especially FAIR and community approved vocabularies)? In several communities, **translation is voluntary**. One of the sustainability challenges is the need for ongoing engagement: how to keep interested groups involved. We need expert translators, as described, to **maintain the quality level critical to achieve effective harmonization** among languages.

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RDA 19th Plenary Meeting, Part Of International Data Week, 20–23 June 2022, Seoul, South Korea

Processes and pathways to disseminate science for wide and efficient reuse

RDA PARSEC data strand Poster :

The image shows a Zenodo poster page for the work "Multilingual Data Challenges in Professionalizing Data Stewardship worldwide". The poster is dated May 27, 2022, and has 529 views and 378 downloads. It is categorized as a "Poster" and is available under "Open Access". The authors listed are David, Romain; Specht, Al; Edmunds, Rorie; Filippone, Clau; and Pignatari Drucker, Debora. The abstract discusses the need for global research collaboration and the use of common FAIR principles. A Twitter overlay is present, showing a tweet by Dr Romain DAVID (9,359 tweets) with 9 likes and 5 retweets. The tweet statistics show 304 impressions, 26 engagements, 0 new followers, 2 profile visits, and 4 clicks on the link. A list of users who followed the tweet is shown, including ResearchDataAlliance, International Technology Office, World Data System, ANR, FRB, Universidade Cidade de São Paulo, and EOSC-Life.

Processes and pathways to disseminate science for wide and efficient reuse

Dissemination Pathway

1. Poster / communication / paper submission / acceptance
 2. Zenodo
 3. Seminar / congress / meetings -> tweet and messages on the poster / sessions
 4. Put it on other archives
 - a. manually e.g. RG
 - b. automated e.g. HAL
 - c. syndication ORCID / pubmed
 - d. Websites (structures / projects / CV / personal page...)
! more your metadata are structured, easier it is
1. Email/tweet/linkedin/... to your communities **!!tagged screenshots!!**
 2. Do it at each milestones (number of views / download) and each related conference / meeting -> **Daily network building** (adding contacts)
 3. Check all PARSEC check lists:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/parsec/?page=1&size=20>

Processes and pathways to disseminate science for wide and efficient reuse

Assessment (as an example)

2576
VIEWS

Viewing Metrics for:
FAIRness Literacy: The Achilles' Heel of Applying FAIR Principles
Published on 11 Aug 2020.

465
DOWNLOADS

- About this Attention Score
- in the top 5% of all research outputs scored by Altmetric
- Mentioned by
 - 3 blogs
 - 97 tweeters
- Citations
 - 12 Dimensions
- Readers on
 - 32 Mendeley

129
TWEETS

FAIRness Literacy: The Achilles' Heel of Applying FAIR Principles
Overview of attention for article published in Data Science Journal, August 2020

85

SUMMARY Blogs Twitter Dimensions citations

You are seeing a free-to-access but limited selection of the activity Altmetric has collected about this research output. [Click here to find out more.](#)

Title: FAIRness Literacy: The Achilles' Heel of Applying FAIR Principles
Published in: Data Science Journal, August 2020
DOI: 10.5334/dsj-2020-032
Authors: Romain David, Laurence Mabille, Alison Specht, Sarah Sryceck, Mogens Thomsen, Mohamed Yahia...

Twitter Demographics Mendeley Readers Attention Score in Context

This research output has an Altmetric Attention Score of 85. This is our high-level measure of the quality and quantity of online attention that it has received. This Attention Score, as well as the ranking and number of research outputs shown below, was calculated when the research output was last mentioned on 16 June 2022.

ALL RESEARCH OUTPUTS	OUTPUTS FROM DATA SCIENCE JOURNAL	OUTPUTS OF SIMILAR AGE	OUTPUTS OF SIMILAR AGE FROM DATA SCIENCE JOURNAL
#400,999 of 22,029,478 outputs	#7 of 326 outputs	#12,094 of 315,788 outputs	#1 of 8 outputs

Altmetric has tracked 22,029,478 research outputs across all sources so far. Compared to these this one has done particularly well and is in the 98th percentile: it's in the top 5% of all research outputs ever tracked by Altmetric.

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To keep in mind

Have
fun!

Catch
eyes!

Take care of yours
take home messages

1. Content
2. Links
3. Community
4. Daily communicate
5. Assess

Special acknowledgements to the data strand of PARSEC

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